

Profile of the Tribal Families from Palghar District

S.K Deshmukh¹, J.R Kadam², S.G Bhave³

Department of Extension Education, College of Agriculture, Dapoli, Ratnagiri- 415712, Maharashtra

Abstract— This paper examines the profile of the tribal families from Palghar district. The study was conducted at the Palghar district. A sample of 120 tribal families were considered as respondents for present study. The respondents were interviewed with the help of specially designed schedule. Collected data was classified, tabulated and analysed by using various statistical method. The result of the study showed that most of the respondents have 'medium' family education status, 'medium' family size, 'medium' annual family income, 'cultivation' as their major occupation, 'marginal' land holding, 'fair' cropping pattern, 'medium' farming experience and 'low' social participation. The extension workers should consider these facts while planning and executing programmes for development of the tribal families living in Palghar district.

Keywords— Profile, Tribal families.

I. INTRODUCTION

Food consumption pattern and food habits is an essential part of any culture. An important part of healthy lifestyle is proper intake of food. The benefits of proper intake of food are observed in wide range of studies. There is a large difference in food consumption pattern of our country India. A balanced diet is required because organs and tissues need proper nutrition to work effectively. The tribal communities have vast knowledge about the importance of consumption of wild plants. These groups are homogenous, culturally firm and wish to survive and live their own lifestyle. The choice of food is deeply related to the lifestyle of an individual. Food habits and consumption pattern is greatly influenced by thoughts, beliefs, notions, traditions and taboos of the society. Apart from these socio-cultural barriers, the religion, education, and economic factors do alter the food behaviour. Government has taken number of measures to overcome hunger and malnutrition. The National Food Security Act, 2013, is the Act of Parliament of India which aims to provide subsidized food grains to approximately two third of India's population. It includes Midday Meal Scheme, Integrated Child Development Services scheme and the Public Distribution System. Even though there are many schemes and nutritional programmes to serve the people, there is a great bulk of illness in our country. Hence, eating good food in one of the pleasures of life.

II. OBJECTIVE

To access the profile of the tribal families from Palghar district.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research work was purposively conducted in Palghar district of Konkanregion of Maharashtra State. Two tahasils Mokhada and Vikramgad having maximum tribal population were selected to carry out the research. Six villages from each tahasil were selected randomly to carry out the present study. A total of 120 tribal families were considered as respondents for the present study. The data was collected with the help of a specially designed interview schedule by keeping in view the objective of the study. Collected data was classified, tabulated and analysed by using various statistical method. 'Ex-post facto' research design was used to conduct the present study.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data in Table 1 indicated that 'majority' (74.16 per cent) of the respondents belonged to 'medium' family education status, while '16.66 per cent' respondents belonged to 'low' family education status and '9.18 percent' of the respondents belonged to 'high' family education status. The average family education status of the respondents was found to be up to 5th standard.

TABLE 1
PROFILE OF THE TRIBAL FAMILIES

Sr. No.	Category	Respondents (N=120)	
		Number	Percentage
Family Education Status			
1.	Low (up to 2 nd std.)	20	16.66
2.	Medium (3 rd – 7 th)	89	74.16
3.	High (8 th and above)	11	9.18
Mean= 5 th Standard Total		120	100
Family Size			
1.	Low (up to 3)	14	11.66
2.	Medium (4-6)	78	78
3.	High (7 and above)	28	23.34
Mean= 5.4 Total		120	100
Annual income of the family			
1.	Low (up to Rs. 24,556/-)	1	0.83
2.	Medium (Rs. 24,557/- to 2,09,083/-)	100	83.34
3.	High (2,09,084/- and above)	19	15.83
Mean= 1,16,820 Total		120	100
Major occupation			
1.	Labour	40	33.34
2.	Caste occupation	0	0.00
3.	Business	2	1.66
4.	Independent profession	9	7.50
5.	Cultivation	57	47.50
6.	Service	12	10.00
Total		120	100
Land holding			
1.	Landless (No land holding)	25	20.83
2.	Marginal (up to 1 ha)	82	68.33
3.	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha)	11	9.16
4.	Semi-medium (2.01 to 4.00 ha)	2	1.68
5.	Medium (4.01 to 10.00 ha)	0	0.00
6.	Big (Above 10.00)	0	0.00
Mean= 0.65 ha Total		120	100
Cropping pattern			
1.	Poor (Up to 2)	27	22.5
2.	Fair (2.1 to 7.9)	70	58.33
3.	Good (8 and above)	23	19.17
Mean= 5.01 Total		120	100
Farming experience			
1.	Low (Up to 5 years)	42	35
2.	Medium (6 to 14 years)	48	40
3.	High (15 years and above)	30	25
Mean = 10 years Total		120	100
Social Participation			
1.	Low (Up to 1)	70	58.34
2.	Medium (2 to 3)	32	26.66
3.	High (4 and above)	18	15
Mean = 2.28 Total		120	100
Resource availability			
1.	Low (Up to 9)	34	28.33
2.	Medium (10 to 11)	48	40.00
3.	High (12 and above)	38	31.67
Mean=10.74 Total		120	100

Regarding family size 'majority' (78.00 per cent) of the tribal family respondents have 'medium' family size, while '23.34 per cent' respondents had 'high' family size and '11.66 per cent' respondents had 'low' family size.

It could be observed that, 'majority' of the tribal family respondents (83.34 per cent) had 'medium' annual family income, while '15.83 per cent' respondents had 'high' family income and only '0.83 per cent' of the respondents had 'low' annual family income. The average annual family income of the tribal families was 'Rs.1,16,820/-'.

The data presented in Table 4 that revealed that, 'nearly half' of the respondents (47.50 per cent) had 'cultivation' as their major occupation, while '33.34 per cent' were 'labours', '10.00 per cent' of them were engaged in 'service', '7.50 per cent' families were engaged in independent profession, only '1.66 per cent' tribal families had 'business' as their profession, and 'no respondents' were engaged in 'caste occupation'.

The data presented reveals that, 'majority' (68.33 per cent) of the respondents had 'marginal' land holding. While '20.83 per cent' of the respondents were 'landless' and '9.16 per cent' and '1.68 per cent' belonged to 'small' and 'semi-medium' category of land holding. No respondents had more than 4 ha of land holding. The average land holding of the respondents was 0.65 ha.

It could be seen that, 'majority'(58.33 per cent) of the respondents had 'fair' cropping pattern, while '22.50 per cent' of respondents had 'poor' and '19.17 per cent' of the respondents have 'good' cropping pattern respectively. The average cropping pattern score of the respondents is 5.01.

It is indicated that, 'majority' of the tribal family respondents (40.00 per cent) had 'medium' farming experience. While '35.00 per cent' had 'low' farming experience and '25.00 per cent' had 'high' farming experience. The average farming experience was 10 years.

It is indicated that, majority of the tribal family respondents (58.34 per cent) had 'low' social participation. While '26.66 per cent' had 'medium' social participation and '15.00 per cent' had 'high' social participation.

V. CONCLUSION

The result of the study showed that most of the respondents have 'medium' family education status, 'medium' family size, 'medium' annual family income, 'cultivation' as their major occupation, 'marginal' land holding, 'fair' cropping pattern, 'medium' farming experience and 'low' social participation. The extension workers should consider these facts while planning and executing programmes for development of the tribal families living in Palghar district.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ananda, S.M and Sahu, U.N., (2012). A Study of Socio-economic and Entrepreneurial Characteristics of Tribals of Mayurbhanj District in Saibai Grass Enterprise. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*. 2(5): 426-438.
- [2] Ayyappan, N. (2014). Developing Integrated Module for Effective functioning of Tribal Women SHG's and their Empowerment. *M.Sc. (Ag.) Thesis*, AC and RI, TNAU, Coimbatore.
- [3] Bakshi. S.R., and Kiran Bala., (2000). Social and Economic Development of Scheduled Tribes. *Deep and Deep publications pvt. Ltd.*, New Delhi.
- [4] Chaudhury, S.S, and Pattanaik D.K., (2016). Traditional Cropping Pattern of Bhumia Tribe-A Case Study from Koraput. *Tribal Studies: A journal of COATS*. <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/316853081>.
- [5] Devika, S. (2012). Non Wood Forest Products (NWFPs) in Improving the Livelihood of Tribal Women, An Explorative Study. *M.Sc. (Ag.) Thesis*. AC and RI, TNAU, Coimbatore.
- [6] Meenakshi Vishwakarma. (2000). A study of food consumption pattern and food analysis of rare foods eaten by Kamars- A primitive tribe of Madhya Pradesh. Ph.D. (Home science) Thesis, PT. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh.